

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO PRODUCTIVE USE OF FREE TIME OF UPPER CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract: Nowadays, effective use of free time of students in general education schools is of great importance. Various spiritual and educational events and sports competitions held in schools help in shaping the education of students, in making them become perfect people in the future, and in forming their worldview. In this study, I collected information based on the opinions of experienced pedagogues and psychologists on the effective use of free time of students and the further increase of students' interest in science, cultural and educational choices.

Key words: Education, contests in schools, students' potential, students' interests, talented students, spiritual and educational activities, students' outlook, modern educational program.

Introduction

Currently, one of the most important tasks of modern schools in the field of education is to educate students to become educated and perfect people. Various spiritual and educational contests, sports competitions, additional classes in subjects organized in schools to increase students' interest in science and meaningful use of their free time increases its potential. In this regard, we analyzed the approaches of experienced pedagogues-psychologists of school education of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on new educational methods. When we analyzed the opinions of many pedagogues, they believed that one of the biggest, but neglected, problems in the process of education and upbringing until now is the lack of serious attention to the issue of the agenda and free time of the growing generation. It is expedient to carry out research on reforming the education and training of young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of modern educational programs and modern scientific methods, based on their needs in the field of education.

One of the important steps in this regard is the adoption of the concept of "Continuous spiritual education" in the modern educational program, using educational programs conducted in specialized schools, presidential schools and private schools. and it will be possible to implement new approaches to education. In this regard, experienced pedagogues-psychologists fully realize the socio-pedagogical possibilities of the family, preschool education, general education, school, secondary special vocational and higher educational

institutions, neighborhoods in guaranteeing the formation of basic qualities in a child. it is determined that it will require the raising of the scientific-methodical unity among them to a new level. More than 60% of our country's population is made up of young people, and modern conditions and opportunities are being created for them to get an education and a profession. In particular, within the framework of the implementation of the President's decision of September 30, 2019 "On measures to fundamentally increase the effectiveness of extracurricular education in the public education system", meaningful organization of the free time of schoolchildren and five important initiatives were put into practice, including comprehensive measures aimed at identifying the creative abilities of the next generation, forming the main content and essence of their development, and at the same time creating additional conditions for youth education. The main task of these schools is to develop children's creative and artistic abilities according to their needs and interests, to organize useful recreation, to inculcate in their hearts diligence and the initial educational skills of professional training. The concept of "free time" is defined as time outside of "professionalism". The problem of free time is a problem considered in legal, psychological, social and medical-physiological aspects, and the fact that it is typical for students of general education schools also shows that it is a pedagogical problem.

In today's modern, changing conditions, the full, systematic and effective realization of the socio-pedagogical potential of teenagers with regard to the correct and effective organization of free time requires enriching the usual areas and forms of work outside of school. The types of activities that can be done in free time are diverse, but due to the limited time, it appears as the most important social value. Leisure activities are divided into socially useful and imaginary (personally important) types. Socially useful free time is a type of free time characterized by the unity of the interests of the individual and society, and neither the individual nor the society is disconnected in any way. In other words, it is a state of activity, a time set aside for relaxation, self-awareness, and entertainment, creating relative freedom from necessary daily activities. Imaginary leisure is aimless entertainment that leads to unusual behavior.

Currently, the psychological and pedagogical problems of high school students are worrying. Because meaningful implementation of students' free time has not been established at the level of demand. It is important to effectively organize the free time of high school students, develop their personal qualities, develop their cognitive interests and abilities, and shape their

worldview. Currently, we can see that most students in 10-11 grades are in the period of choosing a profession and preparing for independent work. During this period, schoolchildren develop self-awareness, realize creative abilities, and set goals for themselves. It is necessary to organize students' culture of using free time not only in extracurricular activities, but also to learn to make the right choice in their daily activities. According to many researchers, the formation of the method of effective use of free time is formed by transitioning from passive-reproductive activity to active creativity, to socially important activities that ensure the spiritual development of a person. Based on the analysis of advanced pedagogical experience, socially significant activities include:

- intellectual, cognitive and creative activities that provide students with the formation of logical thinking skills, creative imagination, consciousness, emotional and aesthetic feelings, special skills and abilities, professional directions;

- socially significant actions that increase students' moral qualities, ability to adapt to the situation, activity.

Every student has his own abilities and talents. Some students are interested in mathematics and physics, while others are interested in history. Pedagogical and psychological questionnaires are conducted during the school period to guide high school students to the profession. Such activities increase the interest of high school students in choosing a free profession.

Conclusion

In the course of these studies, I listened to the opinions of experienced pedagogues and psychologists on the education and training of students in the school education program, on increasing their spiritual and educational potential. The role of teachers is incomparable in shaping students' worldview, increasing their high loyalty to their homeland, people and nation. I talked with many schoolchildren. I witnessed the high level of students' interest in education, culture, and spiritual-educational competitions. By organizing educational events for students who are interested in literature every week, we will help in the formation of students' thinking capacity, mind and spirituality.

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